

EFFECT OF CARBON TYPES ON CURE BEHAVIOR, MORPHOLOGY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF NATURAL RUBBER NANOCOMPOSITE FOAM

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ABSTRACT

Natural rubber nanocomposite foam with carbon particles such as carbon black, graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes was studied in this work to investigate the relationship between foam formation during decomposition of chemical blowing agent mechanism and crosslink reaction of rubber molecules by sulphur. Natural rubber foam with graphene nanoparticles (NRF-G) at the same amount of carbon particle in rubber compound compared to other formulas showed the highest tensile strength with the smallest bubble size in natural rubber nanocomposite foam. The fastest sulphur vulcanization rate of NRF-G resulted in the bubble growth inhibition during processing from high viscosity of cross linked rubber molecules by sulphur. The fastest sulphur vulcanization rate of NRF-G was occurred owing to the remained oxygen functional group of graphene surface after synthesis. This could accelerate sulphur vulcanization reaction by forming a complex species with sulphur vulcanizing agent. Moreover, natural rubber foam with multi-walled carbon nanotubes (NRF-MWCNT) displayed smaller bubble size than natural rubber foam with carbon black (NRF-CB) at the same content and vulcanization rate because the high viscosity from bulk density of MWCNT when compounded in natural rubber system obstructed the bubble growth during processing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Rubber foam is the sponge rubber that has been used in industries due to its light weight, thermal insulation, and sound absorption property [1-6] it can be produced by various methods such as latex process and rubber compound process [7]. The technique of chemical blowing agent decomposition to produce rubber foam is the technique that rubber sheet and all chemicals including chemical blowing agent is mixed as a rubber compound and compressed with pressure at decomposition temperature of chemical blowing agent [2, 7]. There are two main factors that play an important role in mechanical properties of natural rubber foam (NRF) nanocomposites which are sulphur vulcanization reaction rate and effect of filler including filler types, amount of reinforcing filler and surface modification of reinforcing filler [8-11].

The filler can be divided into two categories that are the filler of non-reinforcement and reinforcement in natural rubber matrix. Some of fillers in rubber system are added to reduce cost thus this filler does not increase the mechanical properties of the rubber matrix but it has low price of materials. This type of filler is called non-reinforcing filler in rubber matrix such as calcium carbonate starch and talcum powder [12-14]. Another type of filler in rubber matrix is used to improve mechanical properties of natural rubber matrix which is called reinforcing filler in rubber compound. The reinforcing filler can increase the mechanical properties due to the increment of strength from the property of filler in rubber matrix. There are two types of reinforcing filler that generally used in rubber industries. Firstly, silica particle which is the white reinforcing particle in rubber system is used for producing colour rubber with high mechanical properties due to its white colour that can be mixed with other pigment colours during mixing process. There are many types of silica particle that can be used in rubber compounding system depending on the process preparation and objective of usage. For example, the precipitate silica is used for general purpose because of low price of this silica type while silica nanoparticle produced by sol-gel process is used for special purpose such as high mechanical property with high elasticity from low filler content in rubber [13-15]. Another reinforcing filler in rubber compounding system is the carbon particle. Generally, the carbon particle used in rubber

industries is the carbon black particle produced by pyrolysis of petroleum product or combustion of natural gas industries. Although rubber system with carbon black could increase the mechanical property of rubber composites, it was found that the rubber composite with carbon black should be added high filler content in rubber system to improve mechanical property [16-18]. This might be resulted in high mechanical property with low elasticity of rubber composites owing to the strong and brittle character of filler in rubber matrix. In the recent years, carbon nanocomposite system was introduced. Researchers [18-21] revealed that rubber composite with small amount of carbon nanoparticle improved mechanical and thermal properties. Although, some work [8, 11, 18-21] studied on effect of carbon black and carbon nanoparticle on mechanical and thermal properties of rubber composites, the influence of carbon types on mechanical of natural rubber nanocomposite foam did not investigated from the best of our knowledge. In addition, the effect of graphene and surface treatment of graphene by cyclohexyl diamine from our previous work [11] showed that the nanoparticle content and surface functionalization could accelerate or retarded sulphur vulcanization reaction of natural rubber foam system but the effect of carbon types including carbon black, graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes which were the general carbon reinforcing filler and future carbon reinforcing filler did not be determined.

In this work, natural rubber/carbon composite foam was mixed in two-roll mill and fabricated by compression moulding process. The effect of carbon nanoparticles which were carbon black, graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes on cure characteristics, microstructure and tensile property were investigated.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Air-dried natural rubber sheet with extra light color grade was purchased from Rayong province, Thailand. ZnO, steric acid and sulfur were the commercial grade and used without further purification. N-tert-butyl-2-benzothiazyl sulfenamide (TBBS accelerator) was supported by Sunny World Chemicals Co., Ltd., Thailand. Azodicarbonamide (decomposition temperature of 148 °C) provided by AF Goodrich Chemicals Co., Ltd., Thailand was used as chemical blowing agent. Carbon black was supported by Chemical Village Co., Ltd., Thailand. Graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (Industrial grade) were purchased from Cheap Tubes Inc., USA.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Rubber compounding

200 g of air-dried natural rubber sheet was compounded with 5 phr of ZnO, 2 phr of steric acid, 2.5 phr of TBBS accelerator, 4 phr of azodicarbonamide, 0.5 phr of sulfur and 3 phr of carbon nanoparticles such as carbon black, graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes in two-roll mil at 80°C for 15 minutes. Then, it was stored at room temperature at least 24 hours for releasing stress during mixing process before compressing it in the mold.

2.2.2 Compression molding

Rubber compound was compressed in the metal mold with 17x100x5 mm³ of cavity to produce rubber composite foam specimen at 155°C and 20 bar of pressure with the compression time measured by moving die rheometer (MDR) to observe the microstructure of rubber foam specimen. Another specimen was prepared in the metal mold as a sheet with 2 mm of thickness and cut as a dumbbell shape for tensile measurement. The dimension of tensile testing specimen is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dimension of tensile specimen

2.2.3 Characterization

Cure characteristics of rubber compound was measured by moving die rheometer (Alpha's technologies, RheoTechMD+, USA) at 155°C which was the decomposition temperature of foaming agent. After that, the cure time (t_{c90}) was used as a compression time to produce a rubber foam specimen for observing the microstructure by digital microscope (RoHS, S2, China) with image J software analysis. The tensile specimen from compression moulding process was measured tensile stress by universal testing machine (MTS Sintech, 2S, USA) at 500 mm/min of cross head speed with 10 kN of loading.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cure behavior of natural rubber nanocomposite foam

Cure characteristics of NRF/carbon nanocomposites is shown in Figure 2. It was found from the results that NR/graphene nanocomposite foam (NRF-G) exhibited the fastest vulcanization rate among other formulas due to the effect of remained oxygen functional group on graphene surface from oxidation reaction of graphene oxide synthesis by the supplier. Oxygen functional group on graphene surface such as hydroxyl and carboxylic acid can form the complex structure with sulfenamide accelerator and sulfur to form thiol, thioester, and dithiocarboxylic ester group that can react with sulfur similar to the mechanism of forming a complex species by vulcanization accelerator [22] while NRF with carbon black (NRF-CB) and NRF with multi-walled carbon nanotube (NRF-MWCNT) do not have the oxygen functional group on their surfaces thus they cannot accelerate cure kinetics of natural rubber foam as much as NRF-G nanocomposites.

Figure 2: Cure characteristics of NRF/carbon nanocomposites

3.2 Morphology of natural rubber nanocomposite foam

NRF/carbon composites were observed the microstructure after compression. The morphology of natural rubber composite foam can be seen in Figure 3. The microscopic image of NRF-G nanocomposites displayed the smallest bubble size following by NRF-MWCNT and NRF-CB respectively. The average bubble diameter of NRF/carbon nanocomposites was calculated by arithmetic mean method (\bar{x}) from at least 200 bubbles per formula analyzed by image J software with statistics [9-11]. NRF-G was 81.4 micrometers of bubble size diameter which was the smallest bubble size because it had the fastest vulcanization rate resulting in the fastest time of crosslink between rubber molecules thus it limited the bubble growth during foam formation. Although NRF-CB and

NRF-MWCNT were slightly the same vulcanization rate, they showed different bubble diameter. NRF-MWCNT had slightly larger bubble diameter while NRF-CB showed the largest bubble diameter compared to NRF-G. This might be owing to carbon black particle agglomeration from its nature and low bulk density of MWCNT nanoparticle resulted in smaller bubble size of NRF-MWCNT than NRF-CB composites.

Figure 3: Microstructure of natural rubber nanocomposite foam; a) NRF-CB, b) NRF-G and c) NRF-MWCNT

3.3 Tensile property of natural rubber nanocomposite foam

Rubber foam specimen was measured the tensile property as seen in Figure 4. NRF-G displayed significantly high tensile strength than other formulas caused by the fastest vulcanization rate with the smallest bubble size in natural rubber foam matrix. The small bubble diameter of natural rubber foam exhibited high tensile strength because the small bubble foam inside natural rubber foam matrix would be dispersed the tensile force while the larger bubble diameter would be caused crack initiation easily during tensile testing.

Figure 4: Tensile property of NRF/Carbon nanocomposites

4 CONCLUSION

NRF-G exhibited the fastest vulcanization rate with the smallest bubble diameter among our natural rubber nanocomposite foams in this work because the oxygen functional group on graphene surface via oxidation reaction of graphene synthesis from supplier formed the complex species with sulfur vulcanizing agent. Moreover, NRF-G had the highest tensile strength caused by the smallest sized bubble in natural rubber matrix.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Z. M. Ariff, Z. Zakaria, L. H. Tay, and S. Y. Lee, Effect of foaming temperature and rubber grades on properties of natural rubber foams, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **107**, 2008, pp. 2531-2538.
- [2] N. N. Najib, Z. M. Ariff, N. A. Manan, A. A. Bakar, and C. S. Sipaut, Effect of blowing agent concentration on cell morphology and impact properties of natural rubber foam, *Journal of Physical Science*, **20**, 2009, pp. 13-25.
- [3] N. N. Najib, Z. M. Ariff, A. A. Bakar, and C. S. Sipaut, Correlation between the acoustic and dynamic mechanical properties of natural rubber foam: effect of foaming temperature, *Materials and Design*, **32**, 2011, pp. 505-511.
- [4] M. S. Kim, C. C. Park, S. R. Chowdhury, and G. H. Kim, Physical properties of ethylene vinyl acetate copolymer (EVA)/natural rubber (NR) blend based foam, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **94**, 2004, pp. 2212-2216.
- [5] W. Pechurai, T. Muansupan, and P. Seawlee, Effect of foaming temperature and blowing agent content on cure characteristics, mechanical and morphological properties of natural rubber foams, *Advanced Materials Research*, **844**, 2014, pp. 454-457.
- [6] X. Wang, N. Feng, and S. Chang, Effect of precured degrees on morphology, thermal, and mechanical properties of BR/SBR/NR foams, *Polymer Composites*, **34**, 2013, pp. 849-859.
- [7] A. H. Landlock, *Handbook of plastic foams: types, properties, manufacture and applications*, Park Ridge, New Jersey, 1995.
- [8] J. H. Kim, J. S. Koh, K. C. Choi, J. M. Yoon, and S. Y. Kim, Effects of foaming temperature and carbon black content on the cure characteristics and mechanical properties of natural rubber foams, *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, **13**, 2007, pp. 198-205.
- [9] P. Charoeythornkhajhornchai, C. Samthong, K. Boonkerd, and A. Somwangthanaroj, Effect of azodicarbonamide on microstructure, cure kinetics and physical properties of natural rubber foam, *Journal of Cellular Plastics*, **53**, 2017, pp. 287-303.
- [10] P. Charoeythornkhajhornchai, C. Samthong, and A. Somwangthanaroj, Influence of sulfenamide accelerators on cure kinetics and properties of natural rubber foam, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **134**, 2017, pp. 1-8.
- [11] P. Charoeythornkhajhornchai, C. Samthong, and A. Somwangthanaroj, Effect of graphene treated with cyclohexyl diamine by diazonium reaction on cure kinetics, mechanical, thermal, and physical properties of natural rubber/graphene nanocomposite foam, *Polymer Composites*, **40** (S2), 2019, pp. E1766-E1776.
- [12] N. Tangboriboon, S. Rortchanakarn, K. Petcharoen, and A. Sirivat, Effects of foaming agents and calcium carbonate on thermo-mechanical properties of natural rubber foams, *Polimeri*, **35**, 2015, pp. 10-17.
- [13] V. Pinsanor, S. Junpoonsup, S. Patcharaphun, and N. Sombatsompop, Effects of silica, calcium carbonate, and SiO₂/CaCO₃ blends on properties of cellular NR compounds, *Proceedings of 41st Kasetsart University Annual Conference*, Kasetsart university, Bangkok, February 3-7, 2003, pp. 517-524.
- [14] P. Phaodee, N. Tangjaroensirirat, and C. Sakdaronnarong, Biobased polystyrene foam-like material from crosslinked cassava starch and nanocellulose from sugarcane bagasse, *BioResources*, **10**, 2015, pp. 348-368.

- [15] E. Wimolmala, K. Khongnual, and N. Sombatsompop, Mechanical and morphological properties of cellular NR/SBR vulcanizates under thermal and weathering aging, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **114**, 2009, pp. 2816-2827.
- [16] B. Rodgers, and W. Waddell, *Chapter 14 - Tire Engineering, The science and technology of rubber, 4th edition*, (Eds. J. E. Mark, B. Erman, and C. M. Roland), Boston Academic Press, Boston, 2013, pp. 653-695.
- [17] Samir Majumdar, *Rubber mixing: a practical guide for rubber processing*, Rubber industry academy, Bangkok 2012.
- [18] B. Ozbas, C. D. O'Neill, R. A. Register, I. A. Aksay, R. K. Prud'Homme, and D. H. Adamson, Multifunctional elastomer nanocomposites with functionalized graphene single sheets, *Journal of Polymer Science Part B: Polymer Physics*, **50**, 2012, pp. 910-16.
- [19] L. Zhao, X. Sun, Q. Liu, J. Zhao, and W. Xing, Natural rubber/graphene oxide nanocomposites prepared by latex mixing, *Journal of Macromolecular Science - Physics*, **54**, 2015, pp. 581-592.
- [20] D. H. Fu, Y. H. Zhan, N. Yan, and H. S. Xia, A comparative investigation on strain induced crystallization for graphene and carbon nanotubes filled natural rubber composites, *Express Polymer Letters*, **9**, 2015, pp. 597-607.
- [21] Y. Nakaramontri, C. Kummerlowe, C. Nakason, and N. Vennemann, The effect of surface functionalization of carbon nanotubes on properties of natural rubber/carbon nanotubes composites, *Polymer Composites*, **36**, 2015, pp. 2113-2122.
- [22] J. Wu, W. Xing, G. Huang, H. Li, M. Tang, S. Wu, and Y. Liu, Vulcanization kinetics of graphene/natural rubber nanocomposites, *Polymer*, **54**, 2013, pp. 3314-3323.